

Analysis of Youth's Problems and Interrelation between Problem Areas: A Quantitative Study in Gajraula, Uttar Pradesh

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Abstract

Development of any country depends on its youth . The period can be called as the age of storm ., Young adults are full of energy , where we need to channelize this energy in the right direction . The country which is successful in utilizing the energy of their younger generation will emerge as the powerful and developed nation . It becomes necessary to understand their problem and give them a healthier and better environment , so that they can contribute their fullest in the development of the nation and society . This study aims to find out the problems of youth in Gajraula of Amroha District and the contributing factors behind the problem and correlation between different problem areas. Study conducted on 100 students studying in regular U.G. courses and professional degree courses The study investigated the problems of male and female students and problems of students in regular and professional degree courses. It also find out the correlation between different problem areas.

Keywords Youth, Family Problem, School/College Problem, Social Problem, Personal Problem

Introduction

Younger generation of any country is the asset for it. Young age is known as the period between childhood and adulthood. Merriam webster dictionary consider that young people age ranges from 12 to 24 years. There is no consensus on the age range of young people. It cannot be defined chronologically. Young people can be characterized as energetic , jovial ,full with physical strength. They are supposed to be the future of world. The growth of any country lies in the hand of its youth. This age is considered as the age of storm due to many physical and psychological changes. They need to be understood to grow normally, If the world avoid them or fail to understand them it can increase many psychological and social problems.

Objective of study

1. To find out the Problems of youth studying in under graduate regular and professional courses in Gajraula region.
2. To evaluate the correlation between problem areas and its subsequent personal complications.

Review of Literature

Proctor et al (2009) found in their review of studies that life satisfaction among young people are associated with environmental , social and personality factors , these factors include secure environment , participating in social activities , having healthy familial relationship , enjoying good social relationships etc.

World Economic forum reported 3 issues which is affecting youth today 1st issue reported is that, more than 60 percent of young adults are living with their parents at home in Europe especially in U.S.A. and U.K. ,it may be good for parent but the problem with youngster that they cannot afford their own home. They are facing relatively low level of

socioeconomic mobility. Second issue is working - age life expectancy , In world health ranking India is ranked 117th by WHO , Life expectancy of India increased by 0.33 percent , which is 70.8 now against the global average of 72.8 years. A research concluded that suicidal death is very prominent in Indian women aged between 15 to 49 years. The third issue raised in world economic forum is that , time has come that we must listen to youth while making important decisions (January 2020). Jagriti Kaur , Archana Kaur, Sumit Kumar and Sunil Kumar (2020) found in their study that due to social status , loneliness and depression young student of a reputed university started drinking alcohol , drugs and smoking.

Mamoni Hazarika (2018) wrote in her review paper about the problems being faced by rural youth of Asam. She found that 1) unemployment is one of the problem which is increased by 38% in last 4 years. Due to unavailability of job youths are taking wrong way for their earnings , decrease in mental health can also be seen , adjustment problems, lower self-confidence, increase in poverty level is also there. 2) infrastructure facilities of education is also poor, so the youths are not interested in higher education. 3) There is lack of basic facilities also, which creates transportation, communication, electricity , computer and internet problems, 4) Migration also becoming a big problem among rural youths, youths from rural areas of Asam migrating for work to Gujarat, Hyderabad, Kerala etc. 5) Government or banks are not providing proper funds for startups ,6) Literacy rate is not very high in Asam. 7) Due to the lack of market farmers and others are forced to sold their goods at cheaper rate. 8) apart from that corruption , poverty , lack of education facilities , lack of Government policies are also creating hassles for youths.

Dr Indra Bir Singh Yadav Deputy Director , Skill Development Department wrote in his article "The problem of being youth in India " (31st July 2020) that the peer and family influence on youth is declining on the choice of educational and career selection. Indian youths need more Guidance and counselling. They want upgradation in Education and skilled program , they aspired to acquire new skill development program , which can increase their productivity. young Indians also want better health care facilities , better school facilities , unpolluted and clean environment , good governance , gender equity , opportunity for employment , They want that there must be a space for them to share their ideas , that ideas must be respected , they want both diverse and like-minded people , They want to make tangible difference and experience the world as a classroom.

There is a need of value education for Indian youth due to morality degradation. It is becoming a big problem now a days. Morality degradation creating such problems in society like social unrest , crime , social erosion , separatism etc.

Methodology

In this study "Youth Problem Inventory" was used to collect the data. This scale was developed by Dr. Mithilesh Verma, the inventory consists of 80 items. It is a self-administration inventory for the adolescent students of age to locate the problems in four areas- Family, School/College, Social and Personal area.

The inventory contains 80 statements belonging to the undermentioned 4 areas and a number of sub areas under each main area. Area 'A' measures the problems in family. Sub areas are parental indifference, lack of freedom and parents strict supervision, lack of recognition and criticism by parents, demands, parental interference, parents differentiation between sons and daughters, parental rejection, projection by parents, fear of parents, lack of affiliation, inter generation gap in ideology, sibling relations and overdependence for parents. *Area 'B' measures the problem related to School / College.* That includes fear of teachers and college activities, indifference and rejection by teachers, teachers' incompetence, rude harsh and sarcastic behavior, isolation, difficulties in school/college and subjects. *Area 'C' measures Social Problems.* it includes social inferiorities and social isolation. *Area 'D' is related to Personal Problems.* depressions, logical fears, health and constitutions, manners and habits, beauty consciousness, present and future careers, frustration, personal handicaps, related to feelings of failure and inferiorities. Reliability and Validity: Reliability and validity of inventory is measured and the inventory is both valid and reliable in all areas. Reliability coefficient of area 'A' is.85, area 'B' is.86, area 'C' is.76 and area 'D' is.80. Validity coefficient of Y.P.I. have been found through a number of standardized tests and other techniques. Validity was tested through problem check list (Dr N Bhagia) validity coefficient is found 0.75, through adjustment inventory (Prof H S Asthana) 0.72, Youth adjustment inventory (km Mehru D Bengali).68, through Money problem check list validity coefficient is found.69 etc.

Methodology:

The study was conducted on a normal group of sample size 100, The sample comprised

of age between 17 to 25 years. Sample taken from the students studying in U.G. (regular Courses B.A., B.Sc. and B.Com.), nursing, and B.Ed. (Professional) courses of Gajraula, Amroha district. Researcher contacted with the head of the institution for their approval for data collection, once they got the nod, questionnaires have been distributed among participants, filled questionnaires was collected on next day. Participants were asked to tick only one box for one statement and given the assurance that their response will be kept strictly confidential.

Sampling

The study was conducted on a normal group of sample size 100, The sample comprised of age between 17 to 25 years. Sample taken from the students studying in U.G. (regular Courses B.A., B.Sc. and B.Com.), nursing, and B.Ed. (Professional) courses of Gajraula.

Table -1
Characteristic of respondents (N =100)

	Number	Percentage
Age		
17-25	100	100
Gender		
Male	33	33
Female	67	67
Education		
U.G.(B.A.,B.Sc.,B.Com)	66	66
B.Ed.	17	17
Nursing	17	17

Statistics Used in the Study

Descriptive statistics and correlation method used, data represented graphically (Bar graph)

Result and Discussion

In Table-1 class wise scores of all the participants in different areas are added and mean calculated on the sum. It can be seen in Table 1 that mean score of B.Ed. students are 8.9 in area 'A' which falls in below average category, score in Area 'B' is 1.1 falls in very few category, Area 'C' and 'D' showing the score of .5 and 1.27 these two scores fall under very few and below average category respectively. Students of regular U.G. courses have the mean score in area 'A' i.e. 16.18, in area 'B' 6.93, in area 'C' 1.58, in area 'D' 24.18, area 'A', 'B' and 'C' fall under the category of below average, area 'D' which is related to personal problem is under above average category. Mean score of students of nursing in all four areas are 18.7, 5.2, 0.7, and 13 in 'A', 'B', 'C' and 'D' respectively, in which area 'A' is in average category, except it scores of area 'B' and 'D' are in below average category and area 'C' in very few problem category.

Table – 1
(Education wise score detail in different areas)

	Area 'A'		Area 'B'		Area 'C'		Area 'D'		Total	
	Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.
B.Ed.	8.9	2.55	1.1	1.91	.5	1.27	10.7	4.37	6.32	7.60
U.G.(Regular Courses)	16.18	6.71	6.93	5.27	1.58	1.39	24.18	15.44	12.21	12.33
Nursing	18.7	7.01	5.2	3.12	.7	1.60	13	9.36	9.4	9.14

The result in Table-1 shows that students of B. Ed. are not facing problems which needed to be addressed in any area covered in this study. The scores for the participants of nursing courses is also same as for B.Ed. courses. The students for both of the courses are having good family relations, good college environment, they are also very comfortable in their social settings. They are psychologically more strong than their U.G. counterparts. The participants of U.G. courses are facing problem in area 'D' The score is showing above average problems. It states that they are more frustrated, depressed, anxious about their career. They feel inferior to themselves.

Graph 1

Score distribution in different courses

Graph 1 shows least problem can be seen in area 'C' which is related to social problems is similar for all courses. Area 'D' which is related to personal problems are highest for all courses except nursing students.

In Table 2 percentile score of all classes is shown, This percentile rank is derived by the given norm table of inventory on the basis of mean score given in table 1. Scores in table 2 show the severity of the problem, at what position it stands in the society. It shows the high percentile rank 70 in area 'D' for regular U.G. courses, slightly above average percentile rank 56 in area 'A' for nursing students. Percentile ranks in area 'C' for all degree courses is 11. In area 'B' percentile rank for students of B.A. is highest, it is 34. In area 'A' percentile rank for nursing student is 56, that is highest among all. The percentile rank for students of B.A. is highest in area 'D' states the same result as it discussed earlier.

Table-2
(Education wise Percentile rank in different areas)

	Area 'A'	Area 'B'	Area 'C'	Area 'D'
B.Ed.	15	7	11	20
B.A.	38	34	11	70
Nursing	56	22	11	29

In Table -3 male Respondents in area 'A' have 17.95 (average Category) score and female's score is 14.10, in below average category. In area 'B' male score is 7.30 which is below average though female score 4.85 is also below average. In area 'C' male scored 1.7 and female scored 1.025, these scores are below average and non/Very few categories respectively. Area 'D' is 29.75 for male, That is above average, and female score is 15.23, which is below average. The scores show that student of nursing courses are having more family problems than U.G. regular courses students and B.Ed. students. when we look at the score of area 'D' we will found that U.G. courses students are having more problems than students of any other educational courses.

Table-3
(Gender wise score distribution in different areas)

	Area 'A'		Area 'B'		Area 'C'		Area 'D'	
	Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.
Male	17.95	7.32	7.30	5.41	1.70	1.34	29.75	17.73
Female	14.10	6.41	4.85	4.64	1.025	1.39	15.23	9.51

When we compare the scores for male and female respondent, we will find that there is not much difference between male and female on the basis of problems within family environment, social settings and college environment. We can see the difference in scores of personal problems. Male are facing more problems than females. They are more worried about their future prospects. The uncertainty and low confidence can instigate mere Psychological problems that may lead to mental disorder in future.

Graph-2

(Mean score distribution on various problem areas on gender basis)

In Graph -2 problems in all areas for male and female students look similar. Area 'D' is having maximum problems for both male and female students while in area 'C' both are facing least problems. In all areas female are facing less problems than their male counterparts.

In Table 4 Percentile rank is shown on gender basis. two categories Male and female are there. Percentile rank for each area has been illustrated there. It can be seen that percentile rank for male in area 'A' is highest i.e. 50. In area 'B' 34 and 48 percentile rank in area 'D'. Area 'C' has the lowest percentile 21. For female respondents area 'A' has the highest percentile rank which is 27 all other areas are showing lower percentile rank 22, 17 and 11 for area 'B', 'D' and 'C'. percentile rank of area 'C' is lowest. Percentile rank for male in all area 'A', 'B', 'C' and D are higher than female participants. It indicates that male are facing more problems than female in family in terms of parental indifference, demands by family, parental dominance, lack of affiliation, rejection from parents. In college female students are more comfortable with their teachers. In social situation also female are more comfortable than male. Male respondents are facing more personal problems like illogical fears, personal handicaps etc.

Table - 4
(Percentile Rank in different Areas, Gender wise)

	Area 'A'	Area 'B'	Area 'C'	Area 'D'
Male	50	34	21	48
Female	27	22	11	17

Correlation among all the areas is calculated by Pearson's product moment method and sign test. The result is shown in Table no. 5. It can be seen that Area 'A' and 'B' shares negative correlation. Area 'C' and 'D' have high positive correlation that is significant on.05 level. For B.Ed. courses area 'B' and 'C' shares high positive correlation that is significant on.01 level. In U.G. regular courses there is positive correlation between area 'A' and 'B', which is significant on.01 level. Positive correlation can also be seen between area 'B' and 'C', that is significant on.05 level. Data for female participants show positive correlation between area 'A' and 'B', area 'C' and 'D' significant on.05 level. area 'B' and 'C' and area 'B' and 'D' shares positive correlation significant on.05 level. Some variables also has negative correlation but none of them is found significant, so the chance factor can not be excluded. The correlation chart in table 5 shows that data for nursing student shows that if there is problem in social setting, it will have the same impact on personal problems. if the person is not comfortable in social environment he is facing inferiorities and social isolation it will enhances his personal problems. If we look at the overall correlation analysis of variables, we will find that problems in family having impact on college problems. If the relationship with parents is normal, they are listening to their child, they are not imposing strict discipline over them. These all makes them well-adjusted in college environment also. Educational institutes are like second home for the students, being comfortable in college makes their social adjustment better and decreases their personal problem. Being socially adjusted reduces their personal problems, if they are socially withdrawn their personal problem will increase.

Table-5
(Correlation between areas)

		A & B	A & C	A & D	B & C	B & D	C & D
1.	Pearson product moment	.428**	.267	.055	.443**	.391**	.276*
2.	Sign test	.001	.039	.676	.000	.002	.033

*significant at .05 level

**Significant at .01 level

Table 6 showing the overall data for the questionnaire in all the areas. the score in area 'A ' is 15.383. the problems are in below average category. Mean score of Area 'B ' and area 'C ' is also in below average category. Mean score of Area 'D ' is slightly higher than all other areas and it falls under average category. Correlation between variables are shown in table no. 7. It is showing positive and significant correlation between area A & B, area B & C, area B&D, area C & D. It shows that problem in family affects the adjustment in college. problems in college makes social adjustment difficult, it also enhances personal problems. The correlation between area 'A ' and 'B ' is significant on .01 level. It indicates that Family problems and college problems are moderately positively correlated. when family problem increases college problems will also increase. Perera, Rasanjalee (2012) have also find in their study that family background influences the problems of college student whether it is Social, financial, Psychological and educational. If there is less problems in family student will also perform better in college environment. Area 'B ' and 'C ' is also positively correlated. The correlation between area 'B and 'C ' is moderate. it states that college problems and social problems are correlated. The young adults who prefers to be isolated and do not like to take part in social activities are also not performing well in college. Area 'B 'and 'D 'is also positively correlated. It clarifies that college problem increases with the increase in personal problems. Correlation between area 'C ' and 'D ' suggest that problems in social situation increases the problem in personal area also.

Table-6
(Overall statistical analysis of data)

	Area "A"	Area "B"	Area "C"	Area "D"	Total
Mean	15.383	5.67	1.25	15.225	9.382
S.D.	6.91	5.00	1.39	9.51	5.7025

Pie chart -1

Graph-3 : Score distribution in all problem areas

The pie chart is showing problems of youth in various spheres of life. Problems in area 'A ' consists 41% of overall problems, sharing the equal proportion with area 'D ' which also consists 41% problems. It describes that family problems and personal problems are causing much pressure on today's youth. Parents are strict in posing discipline on their wards. Their expectation are too high as per the capability of their son/daughter. Students are found most affected by projection and interference of parents, they are supposed to carry out the ideals of their parents. Students found it more problematic when their parents are interfering in their personal space. Students are more vulnerable to criticism by others, it creates problems which can leads to depressed mood. Students

are least affected by the problems of their educational institute, this area consist only 15% of their problems and at last social problems is weighing only 3% of their total problems.

Findings

1. No severe Problem of the youths, studying in regular and professional courses in Gajraula has been detected .
2. Problem areas such as Family and college problems, College and social problems, college and personal problems , social and personal problems are positively correlated. Therefore the hypothesis that there will be a correlation between different problem areas is true.

Conclusion

As we discussed earlier, we can find that problems of the students are not very much complicated. Scores are showing the problem in personal sphere and in family environment, but these problems are not on serious note. It is same for the students of all educational background covered in this study. If we see the result of male and female students, it is found that male students are having more problems in personal sphere in comparison to their female counterparts. They are facing more problems in their family and personal life as well. All the factors that are creating problems in life, are interrelated. Problems in one sphere create problems in another sphere. Family problems can enhance the problems of college. Saeko Kamoshida, Naoto Nihonmatsu, Gen Takagi, Koubun Wakashima (June 2022) conducted a study to find out the correlation between family problems and family variables. The researcher also found the same result that family variables are associated with family social problems. College problem is associated with social and personal problem This study is in line with the study of V. Perez, E.L. Gesten et al, they found a differential relationship between specific family problems and problem solving skills. Social problems make it difficult to adjust in personal area. Having problem in one area instigate the problems in other areas also, that can multiply the overall problem.

Suggestions for the future Study

As we discussed earlier , we can find that problems of the students are not very much complicated . Scores are showing the problem in personal sphere and in family environment , but these problems are not on serious note . It is same for the students of all educational background covered in this study . If we see the result of male and female students , it is found that male students are having more problems in personal sphere in comparison to their female counterparts . They are facing more problems in their family and personal life as well . All the factors that are creating problems in life , are interrelated . Problems in one sphere create problems in another sphere . Family problems can enhance the problems of college . Saeko Kamoshida , Naoto Nihonmatsu , Gen Takagi , Koubun Wakashima (June 2022) conducted a study to find out the correlation between family problems and family variables . The researcher also found the same result that family variables are associated with family social problems. College problem is associated with social and personal problem This study is in line with the study of V. Perez , E.L. Gesten et al, they found a differential relationship between specific family problems and problem solving skills . Social problems make it difficult to adjust in personal area . Having problem in one area instigate the problems in other areas also , that can multiply the overall problem . A study can be done on larger sample.

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